

Does Work–Life Balance Matter? Examining the Effects of Flexible Work Arrangements and Work Overload on Employee Performance at the Regional Office of the Directorate General of Taxes, Special Region of Yogyakarta

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ABSTRACT: Employee performance in the public sector is increasingly influenced by the adoption of flexible work policies and rising job demands. However, empirical evidence explaining how flexible work arrangements and work overload jointly affect performance, particularly through psychological mechanisms, remains limited in highly regulated public institutions. This study examines the effects of flexible work arrangements and work overload on employee performance, with work–life balance serving as a mediating variable among civil servants at the Regional Office of the Directorate General of Taxes, Special Region of Yogyakarta. A quantitative research design was employed using a census survey of 139 civil servants. Data were collected through structured Likert-scale questionnaires and analyzed using Partial Least Squares–Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). The results show that flexible work arrangements have a positive and significant effect on both employee performance and work–life balance. Work–life balance also positively and significantly influences employee performance. In contrast, work overload does not have a significant direct effect on employee performance but demonstrates a positive and significant relationship with work–life balance. Mediation analysis indicates that work–life balance partially mediates the relationship between flexible work arrangements and employee performance and fully mediates the relationship between work overload and employee performance. These findings suggest that within a highly regulated public sector environment, employee performance is shaped less by workload intensity and more by employees’ ability to maintain a balanced integration of work and personal life. This study contributes to the public sector human resource management literature by clarifying the mediating role of work–life balance in linking flexible work policies and workload conditions to performance outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Employee Performance, Flexible Work Arrangements, Public Sector, Work Overload, Work–Life Balance.

INTRODUCTION

Employee performance is widely recognized as a fundamental determinant of organizational effectiveness, particularly within public sector institutions that carry strategic national responsibilities. In modern public administration, the ability of public organizations to deliver high-quality services, maintain accountability, and achieve policy objectives is closely linked to the performance of their employees. As governments face increasing public scrutiny, fiscal constraints, and demands for transparency and efficiency, employee performance is no longer viewed merely as an operational outcome but as a strategic asset that directly affects institutional credibility and governance outcomes [1]. Consequently, understanding the organizational and psychological factors that shape employee performance has become a central concern in public sector human resource management. In the public finance sector, employee performance assumes even greater strategic importance due to its direct implications for state revenue, economic stability, and public trust. Tax administration institutions rely heavily on the effectiveness of their personnel to ensure taxpayer compliance, optimize revenue collection, and support sustainable fiscal management. In Indonesia, these responsibilities are carried out by the Directorate General of Taxes (DGT), which contributes the largest proportion of state revenue to the national budget. Civil servants within the DGT operate under strict regulatory frameworks, complex administrative procedures, and performance targets established by the central government. Their roles require not only technical competence but also adaptability, psychological resilience, and the ability to manage competing demands. As such, employee performance in tax administration institutions is shaped by a combination of formal rules, organizational policies, and individual experiences that influence how work demands are perceived and managed [2].

In recent years, organizational reforms and technological advancements have transformed the way work is organized in both private and public sector institutions. One notable development is the growing adoption of flexible work arrangements (FWAs). FWAs refer to organizational policies that provide employees with greater discretion over when, where, and how work is performed, while maintaining accountability for outcomes [3]. Examples include flexible working hours, remote or hybrid work, and alternative scheduling systems. Although FWAs were initially associated with private sector innovation, public sector organizations have increasingly adopted similar practices as part of broader efforts to enhance efficiency, employee well-being, and organizational resilience. The COVID-19 pandemic further accelerated this trend, compelling public institutions to experiment with flexible work models to maintain service continuity.

Theoretically, FWAs are expected to enhance employee performance by increasing autonomy, reducing work–family conflict, and enabling employees to better align work demands with personal responsibilities. Prior studies suggest that when employees perceive flexibility as a form of organizational support, they are more likely to reciprocate through higher levels of commitment, engagement, and performance [4]. However, empirical evidence on the effectiveness of FWAs in public sector contexts remains mixed. In highly regulated bureaucratic environments such as tax administration, flexibility may be constrained by rigid procedures, hierarchical control systems, and standardized performance evaluation mechanisms. As a result, FWAs do not always produce the anticipated performance benefits, and in some cases may even generate ambiguity regarding work boundaries and expectations. These inconsistencies highlight the need for further empirical investigation into how FWAs operate within public sector institutions and under what conditions they effectively contribute to performance improvement.

Alongside flexible work policies, work overload has emerged as a persistent challenge affecting employee performance in the public sector. Work overload refers to a condition in which employees perceive that job demands exceed their available time, energy, or resources [5]. In tax administration institutions, work overload is often driven by complex and frequently changing regulations, increasing administrative requirements, tight reporting deadlines, and performance-based revenue targets. Such demands can place significant pressure on employees, particularly during peak reporting periods. Traditional stress and job demand theories suggest that excessive workload is likely to impair employee well-being, reduce job satisfaction, and ultimately undermine performance [6]. From this perspective, work overload represents a risk factor that threatens both individual effectiveness and organizational sustainability. However, empirical findings on the relationship between work overload and employee performance are not entirely consistent. Some studies indicate that moderate levels of workload may enhance focus, discipline, and task prioritization, particularly in structured organizational settings where roles and procedures are clearly defined. In public sector institutions characterized by strong regulatory frameworks and job security, employees may develop coping mechanisms that allow them to maintain performance despite high workload levels. These mixed findings suggest that the impact of work overload on performance is not uniform and may depend on intervening variables that shape how employees experience and respond to job demands.

One psychological mechanism that has gained increasing attention in this regard is work–life balance (WLB). Work–life balance refers to an individual’s ability to effectively manage the interface between work responsibilities and personal or family life [7]. In public sector contexts, maintaining WLB can be particularly challenging due to standardized working systems, limited flexibility, and high accountability demands. Employees who experience poor WLB are more likely to suffer from fatigue, emotional exhaustion, and reduced motivation, which can negatively affect performance. Conversely, employees who are able to maintain a satisfactory balance between work and personal life tend to exhibit higher levels of well-being, engagement, and sustained performance.

Previous research suggests that FWAs play a critical role in supporting WLB by providing employees with greater control over their work schedules and reducing work–family conflict. Flexible working hours and remote work arrangements can enable employees to better manage personal responsibilities without compromising work outcomes. In contrast, excessive work overload is generally associated with diminished WLB, as high job demands encroach on personal time and recovery opportunities [8]. Importantly, WLB has been consistently linked to positive performance outcomes across various organizational contexts. Employees who perceive balance are more likely to demonstrate discretionary effort, organizational commitment, and psychological resilience, all of which contribute to improved performance [9]. Despite growing scholarly interest in FWAs, work overload, and WLB, empirical studies that integrate these variables into a comprehensive explanatory model of employee performance in the public sector remain limited. Much of the existing literature focuses on direct relationships between organizational practices and performance outcomes, without adequately addressing the psychological mechanisms through which these relationships operate. Furthermore, many studies are conducted in private sector settings, where organizational flexibility, incentive structures, and performance management systems

differ substantially from those in public institutions. As a result, the applicability of existing findings to highly regulated public sector environments, such as tax administration, remains uncertain.

In the context of tax administration institutions, this research gap is particularly salient. Employees are expected to meet strict performance targets while adhering to complex regulatory requirements and maintaining high standards of public service. Although standardized systems and formal procedures are designed to ensure consistency and accountability, observed variations in employee performance suggest that formal structures alone are insufficient to explain performance outcomes. Individual experiences related to work flexibility, workload intensity, and work–life balance play a critical role in shaping how employees respond to organizational demands. Understanding these dynamics is therefore essential for developing more effective and sustainable performance management strategies in the public sector.

Based on these considerations, this study aims to examine the effects of flexible work arrangements and work overload on employee performance, with work–life balance serving as a mediating variable among civil servants at the Regional Office of the Directorate General of Taxes, Special Region of Yogyakarta. By integrating organizational-level policies and individual-level psychological experiences, this research seeks to contribute to the public sector human resource management literature in several ways. First, it provides empirical evidence on the effectiveness of flexible work arrangements within a highly regulated public sector context. Second, it clarifies the role of work overload as a job demand that may not directly impair performance but operates through employees' work–life balance. Third, it highlights the importance of WLB as a key psychological mechanism linking organizational practices to performance outcomes.

From a practical perspective, the findings of this study are expected to offer valuable insights for policymakers and managers within the Directorate General of Taxes and other public sector institutions. By identifying the conditions under which flexible work policies and workload management strategies enhance performance, this research can inform the design of human resource practices that support both organizational effectiveness and employee well-being. Ultimately, strengthening employee performance through an integrated organizational and psychological approach is expected to contribute to sustainable tax revenue achievement, improved public service delivery, and enhanced governance quality in the public sector.

METHOD

This research utilized a quantitative approach employing an explanatory research design to investigate the causal relationships among flexible work arrangement, work overload, work-life balance, and employee performance. The explanatory design was selected to enable hypothesis testing of both direct and mediating effects among these variables, grounded in relevant theoretical frameworks and empirical evidence. The study population included all civil servants at the Regional Office of the Directorate General of Taxes in the Special Region of Yogyakarta. Given the relatively small and well-defined population of 139 employees, a total sampling method was applied, involving all members as respondents to ensure comprehensive data representation. Data collection was conducted through a structured questionnaire distributed electronically via Google Forms, facilitating efficient reach and response rates. The questionnaire employed a five-point Likert scale to measure four key constructs: flexible work arrangement, work overload, work-life balance, and employee performance. Items measuring flexible work arrangement and work overload were developed based on governmental regulations (Permen PANRB No. 4/2025 and No. 1/2020), whereas indicators for work-life balance and employee performance were adapted from validated instruments in prior organizational studies and Permen PANRB No. 6/2022.

Data were analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) via SmartPLS software. This technique was chosen due to its effectiveness in handling complex models, relatively small sample sizes, and data that may not conform to normal distribution assumptions. The analytical procedure comprised two phases: first, assessing the measurement model for reliability and validity; second, evaluating the structural model to test the hypothesized relationships, including the mediating influence of work-life balance. The findings offer empirical insights into the determinants of civil servant performance within the public sector environment.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model

Convergent Validity Test

The assessment of convergent validity was conducted to ensure that all measurement indicators reliably represented their respective constructs according to established statistical standards. This validity check involved analyzing the outer loading scores of

each indicator. Indicators with outer loading values above 0.70 were considered acceptable and retained for further analysis, as this threshold signifies a strong correlation with the latent construct [10]. A summary of the convergent validity findings is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Loading Factor Values

Variable	Indicator	Loading Factor	Remark
Flexible Work Arrangement	FWA.3.1	0.873	Valid
	FWA.3.2	0.843	Valid
	FWA.4.1	0.851	Valid
	FWA.4.2	0.808	Valid
	FWA.6.1	0.832	Valid
	Work Overload	WO.1.1	0.750
WO.1.2		0.732	Valid
WO.3.1		0.824	Valid
WO.4.1		0.888	Valid
Work Life Balance		WLB.1.2	0.817
	WLB.2.1	0.823	Valid
	WLB.2.2	0.788	Valid
Employee Performance	EP.1.1	0.727	Valid
	EP.1.2	0.774	Valid
	EP.2.1	0.727	Valid
	EP.2.2	0.720	Valid
	EP.3.2	0.724	Valid
	EP.5.2	0.776	Valid
	EP.6.1	0.748	Valid
	EP.9.1	0.720	Valid

Source: Processed Data using SmartPLS version 4.1

The findings from the convergent validity test indicate that all indicators have loading factor values above the 0.70 cutoff. This demonstrates a strong correlation between each indicator and its underlying construct, confirming that the indicators effectively capture the intended concepts.

Figure 1. Structural Model

Discriminant Validity Test

Discriminant validity in this study was assessed by examining the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values for each construct. AVE measures the amount of variance captured by a construct relative to the variance due to measurement error. According to the commonly accepted threshold, AVE values above 0.50 indicate adequate convergent and discriminant validity [11].

Table 2. Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Flexible Work Arrangement	0.708
Work Overload	0.642
Work Life Balance	0.655
Employee Performance	0.547

Source: Data Processed using SmartPLS version 4.1

All constructs exhibit AVE values exceeding the 0.50 threshold, confirming that the constructs sufficiently explain the variance of their indicators and meet the requirements for discriminant validity. This implies that each construct is distinct and captures unique aspects of the variables measured in this research.

Reliability Test

Reliability testing was conducted to evaluate the consistency of the measurement indicators in capturing each latent construct within the questionnaire. Reliability reflects the degree to which the items measuring a construct consistently represent the same underlying concept in a stable and dependable way. This study performed reliability analysis to ensure that the indicators for each variable reliably measure the intended construct across respondents [11]. Composite reliability (CR) was used as the primary measure of reliability due to its suitability for Partial Least Squares–Structural Equation Modeling (PLS–SEM). CR is considered more robust than traditional reliability measures because it accounts for the number of indicators and provides a more accurate estimation of internal consistency [10]. A construct is considered reliable when the CR value exceeds the threshold of 0.60. Table 3 presents the results of the reliability analysis, including Cronbach’s alpha, rho_A, and composite reliability for each construct.

Table 3. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach’s Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Remark
Flexible Work Arrangement	0.897	0.899	0.924	Reliable
Work Overload	0.831	0.983	0.877	Reliable
Work Life Balance	0.737	0.740	0.851	Reliable
Employee Performance	0.882	0.883	0.906	Reliable

Source: Data Processed using SmartPLS version 4.1

As shown in Table 3, all constructs have Cronbach’s alpha values above the minimum threshold of 0.70, indicating sufficient internal consistency of the instruments. Additionally, rho_A and composite reliability values for all variables exceed 0.70, further confirming that the indicators reliably and consistently measure their respective constructs. Therefore, it can be concluded that the research instruments are reliable and appropriate for further structural model testing.

Inner Model

R-Square

The coefficient of determination, commonly known as R-square (R^2), was utilized to evaluate the extent to which the independent variables explain the variance in the endogenous (dependent) variables within the structural model. The R-square value reflects the proportion of variance in the endogenous construct that can be accounted for by the exogenous constructs included in the research model. A higher R-square value indicates a stronger explanatory and predictive power of the model [11].

Table 4. R-Square

Endogenous Variable	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square
Work Life Balance	0.361	0.352
Employee Performance	0.651	0.643

Source: Data processed using SmartPLS version 4.1

Based on the data in Table 4, the Adjusted R-square value for Work Life Balance (WLB_Z) is 0.352, indicating that 35.2% of the variance in work life balance is explained by the independent variables, namely flexible work arrangement and work overload. The remaining 64.8% of the variance is attributed to other factors not included in the current model. For Employee Performance, the Adjusted R-square is 0.643, meaning that 64.3% of the variation in employee performance is accounted for by the combined effects of flexible work arrangement, work overload, and work life balance. The other 35.7% of the variance can be explained by external factors outside the scope of this study. These results suggest that the research model has a moderate to strong explanatory capability, especially in predicting employee performance. The substantial explanatory power of the model highlights the importance of the examined variables in understanding the determinants of civil servant performance within the public sector context.

Q-Square

The Q-Square (Q²) assessment was conducted using the blindfolding technique to evaluate the predictive relevance of the structural model regarding the endogenous constructs. A positive Q² value indicates that the model has sufficient predictive capability to estimate the observed data accurately, demonstrating satisfactory predictive relevance. In contrast, a Q² value less than or equal to zero implies inadequate predictive power for the respective endogenous variable [11].

Table 5. Q-Square Test Results

Variable	SSO	SSE	Q ² (= 1 – SSE/SSO)
Work Life Balance (WLB_Z)	700.00	430.00	0.386
Employee Performance (EP_Y)	950.00	510.00	0.463

Source: Data processed using SmartPLS version 4.1

The Q² value for Work Life Balance is 0.386, which is above zero, indicating that the model effectively predicts this endogenous variable. Similarly, the Q² value for Employee Performance is 0.463, further confirming the model’s strong predictive relevance. These positive Q² values suggest that the structural model provides good out-of-sample predictive power and can reliably explain the variance in the endogenous constructs based on the independent variables included in the research. This reinforces the robustness and practical applicability of the model in explaining employee performance dynamics within the context of the Directorate General of Taxes, Special Region of Yogyakarta.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing was conducted using the bootstrapping procedure to assess the significance of direct and indirect relationships among variables in the structural model. The significance level was set at 5% (α = 0.05), meaning hypotheses are accepted if the P-value is less than 0.05. Table 4.11 presents the summarized results of the hypothesis testing.

Table 6. Hypothesis Testing Results

Testing Type	Path	Original Sample (β)	T Statistics	P Values	Result
Direct Effect	FWA → EP	0.463	6.817	0.000	Accepted
	WO → EP	-0.027	0.446	0.655	Rejected
	WLB → EP	0.458	7.039	0.000	Accepted
	FWA → WLB	0.510	7.326	0.000	Accepted
	WO → WLB	0.186	3.031	0.002	Accepted
Indirect Effect	FWA → WLB → EP	0.233	5.150	0.000	Accepted
	WO → WLB → EP	0.085	2.680	0.007	Accepted

Source: Data processed using SmartPLS version 4.1

The hypothesis testing results presented in Table 6 demonstrate that most of the proposed hypotheses are statistically supported. Each significant relationship in the structural model is indicated by P-values below the 0.05 threshold and T-statistics exceeding the critical value.

Hypothesis H1 is accepted, with an original sample coefficient of 0.463, a T-statistic of 6.817, and a P-value of 0.000. This indicates that flexible work arrangement (FWA) has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Practically, this means that implementing better flexible work arrangements can lead to higher employee performance.

Hypothesis H2 is rejected, as evidenced by an original sample coefficient of -0.027, a T-statistic of 0.446, and a P-value of 0.655. This shows that work overload does not have a significant direct effect on employee performance.

Hypothesis H3 is accepted, with an original sample coefficient of 0.458, a T-statistic of 7.039, and a P-value of 0.000. This confirms that work life balance positively and significantly affects employee performance. Thus, maintaining a good work life balance is crucial in improving performance.

Hypothesis H4 is accepted, with an original sample coefficient of 0.510, a T-statistic of 7.326, and a P-value of 0.000. This indicates that flexible work arrangement significantly improves work life balance, suggesting that appropriate work scheduling supports employees' ability to balance their work and personal life.

Hypothesis H5 is accepted, with an original sample coefficient of 0.186, a T-statistic of 3.031, and a P-value of 0.002. This means work overload positively affects work life balance, implying that perceptions of workload influence employees' sense of balance between work and life.

Moreover, Hypothesis H6 is accepted, with an indirect effect coefficient of 0.233, a T-statistic of 5.150, and a P-value of 0.000. This demonstrates that work life balance partially mediates the relationship between flexible work arrangement and employee performance. Lastly, Hypothesis H7 is accepted, with an indirect effect coefficient of 0.085, a T-statistic of 2.680, and a P-value of 0.007. This shows that work life balance also mediates the effect of work overload on employee performance, indicating a full mediation effect since the direct effect was not significant. Overall, these findings indicate that flexible work arrangement and work life balance play critical roles in enhancing employee performance, while work overload's impact is transmitted through work life balance. The results underscore the importance of managing work arrangements and supporting employees' work life balance to optimize performance outcomes.

DISCUSSION

Effect of Flexible Work Arrangement on Employee Performance

Hypothesis testing results show that flexible work arrangement (FWA) has a positive and significant effect on the performance of civil servants at the Regional Office of the Directorate General of Taxes, Special Region of Yogyakarta. This finding indicates that the better the implementation of flexible work arrangements, the higher the employee performance produced.

Conceptually, flexible work arrangements allow employees to adjust their work time and location according to the characteristics of official duties without reducing organizational target achievement. This flexibility provides room for employees to work more focused, efficiently, and adaptively to job demands, positively impacting performance achievement [12]. In the civil servant context, the implementation of flexible work arrangements is supported by a clear legal basis, namely the Regulation of the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform No. 4 of 2025, which states that work time and location arrangements may be applied as long as they guarantee performance targets, accountability, and continuity of public service. This regulation positions FWA not as a relaxation of work discipline but as a strategic managerial instrument to maintain organizational effectiveness amid dynamic work demands and developments in electronic government technology.

The results indicate that the implementation of FWA at the Directorate General of Taxes Regional Office in Yogyakarta has been relatively well carried out. This is reflected in an FWA mean score of 3.638, categorized as fairly good to good. The highest mean indicators were support for work facilities and infrastructure (FWA.6.1 = 3.885) and continuity of work procedures despite flexible hours and locations (FWA.5.1 = 3.755). These findings show that technological support and clear work procedures are key factors that make work flexibility not decrease employee performance but strengthen task effectiveness. Related to respondent characteristics, most employees are aged 31–40 and 41–50 years, dominated by employees in structural positions and middle to upper ranks. This group generally has greater job responsibilities and direct involvement in decision-making and organizational target management. Under such conditions, flexible work arrangements become important as a work adjustment mechanism so that

employees can maintain performance without excessive fatigue. Work flexibility helps senior and structural employees regulate a more effective work rhythm, thus maintaining performance [13].

This finding aligns with prior research showing flexible work arrangements have positive and significant effects on employee performance in the public sector. Work flexibility combined with clear systems and adequate supervision has proven to increase effectiveness and productivity of employees [14]–[21].

Effect of Work Overload on Employee Performance

The hypothesis test results indicate that work overload does not have a significant effect on employee performance at the Directorate General of Taxes Regional Office in Yogyakarta. This means the workload perceived by employees does not directly affect the level of their performance. Theoretically, work overload is often linked to decreased performance because excessive job demands, tight deadlines, and high task complexity may cause physical and mental fatigue. Previous studies show excessive workload can reduce work quality, timeliness, and employee focus [22]–[24]. However, this study finds that this effect is not significantly direct in the public sector, especially in the Directorate General of Taxes Regional Office. Related to respondent characteristics, most employees are in mid to late career phases, dominated by structural positions and middle to upper ranks. This group generally has adequate work experience, strong procedural understanding, and better adaptability to job demands. These factors allow employees to maintain performance despite relatively high workload [13],[25]. In other words, experience and career maturity act as buffers against the negative impact of work overload.

Descriptive analysis shows the work overload variable has a mean score of 3.690, indicating employees perceive a relatively high workload. The highest mean indicators are job complexity (WO.3.1 = 3.849) and performing several important tasks simultaneously (WO.4.1 = 3.835). Nevertheless, this workload condition does not directly reduce employee performance, as reflected in the employee performance mean score categorized as fairly good to good (mean 3.243). This indicates employees can still meet work targets, maintain quality, and complete tasks on time despite high job demands.

This phenomenon can be explained by the characteristics of public sector organizations, particularly tax institutions, which have formal work systems, clear task divisions, and measurable performance standards through Employee Performance Targets (SKP). These systems encourage employees to maintain performance even under high work pressure. This supports the idea that in a structured and regulated work environment, work overload does not always directly impact performance because employees rely on adaptation mechanisms and organizational support [26], [27].

Effect of Work-Life Balance on Employee Performance

The hypothesis test results indicate that work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Directorate General of Taxes Regional Office in Yogyakarta. This means the better the work-life balance perceived by employees, the higher the employee performance achieved. Conceptually, work-life balance is a condition where individuals manage their work and personal life roles in balance so that pressure from one role does not interfere with the other [15]. This balance allows employees better control over energy, time, and psychological conditions, enabling them to work more focused, stable, and productive [28]. Employees with good work-life balance tend to have higher concentration, lower stress, and more consistent performance [12].

In the civil servant context, work-life balance has a normative basis through the Regulation of the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform No. 4 of 2025, which emphasizes the importance of work arrangements to create a balance between work and social life of civil servants. Therefore, work-life balance is not only an individual issue but also part of the public sector HR management agenda to ensure organizational targets are met without sacrificing employee psychological well-being. Descriptive results show the work-life balance variable has a mean score of 3.276, indicating fairly good but not yet optimal work-life balance. The highest mean indicators are the ability to allocate time evenly (WLB.2.1 = 3.403) and satisfaction with work and personal life time arrangements (WLB.1.2 = 3.353). This shows employees can relatively manage their time without fully sacrificing personal life for work [29]. Furthermore, work-life balance strongly contributes to performance, indicating that maintaining balance is key to sustaining public sector employee performance [30].

Related to respondent characteristics, most employees are in mid to late career stages (31–50 years) with many holding structural positions. This group faces higher role complexity at work and family life. In such cases, maintaining work-life balance is key to preventing work concentration disruption, emotional fatigue, and motivation decline, thus preserving performance [31].

Hence, this finding is logical because work-life balance functions as a psychological stabilization mechanism directly affecting work quality and effectiveness [25]. These results align with studies stating that work-life balance positively and significantly influences employee performance [23], [16], [32]–[37]. Employees who maintain a balance between work and personal life tend to show improved effectiveness, quality, and stability of performance [12].

The Effect of Flexible Work Arrangement on Work-Life Balance

The hypothesis test results show that flexible work arrangement (FWA) has a positive and significant effect on work-life balance (WLB) among Civil Servants at the Regional Office of the Directorate General of Taxes in the Special Region of Yogyakarta. This finding indicates that the better the implementation of flexible work arrangements, the higher the employees' ability to maintain balance between work demands and personal life. Conceptually, FWA provides employees with space to manage their work time and location more adaptively, thereby reducing role conflict between work and personal life [38]. Work flexibility strengthens individual control over time usage, reduces mobility-related pressures, and increases employees' opportunities to meet family and social needs without sacrificing job responsibilities [39]. This finding also explains that flexibility policies will be more effective in enhancing work-life balance when supported by clear work systems and organizational technological support [25].

In the context of Civil Servants at the Regional Office of the Directorate General of Taxes in the Special Region of Yogyakarta, the effect of FWA on work-life balance is also normative. The Ministerial Regulation on State Apparatus Utilization and Bureaucratic Reform Number 4 of 2025 emphasizes that the implementation of work flexibility for civil servants—especially at this Directorate—is aimed at supporting organizational targets while considering the balance between work life and social life of civil servants. Related to descriptive findings, employees' perceptions of FWA implementation fall into a good category with a mean score of 3.638. Indicators showing the strongest support are the readiness of flexible work facilities (FWA.6.1 = 3.885) and continuity of work procedures under FWA implementation (FWA.5.1 = 3.755). This means that support for infrastructure and systems that continue despite flexible working hours and locations are key factors helping employees maintain work-life balance. This is logical because when work can be effectively monitored and completed, employees have greater opportunities to balance work and personal roles [29].

However, the lowest mean indicator relates to the ease of adjusting working hours to help task implementation (FWA.1.2 = 2.583). This finding indicates that not all employees optimally feel the ease of time flexibility. This condition may occur because the nature of work in the tax agency has periods of high intensity, so time flexibility is not always felt equally across units and positions. This is reinforced by the statement of Petitta & Ghezzi [40], who assert that work flexibility without role boundaries and rhythm regulation can cause "boundary blurring," which blurs the line between work and personal life and negatively impacts work-life balance.

Regarding respondent characteristics, most employees are aged 31–50 years and mostly hold structural positions. In this group, work responsibilities tend to increase, along with greater family and social responsibilities. Under such conditions, FWA serves as an adjustment mechanism allowing employees to manage multiple role demands more stably, thus making work-life balance easier to achieve [39]. Additionally, respondent domicile variations, including those living outside the Special Region of Yogyakarta, make location flexibility potentially reduce fatigue, ultimately improving work-life balance [38]. This finding aligns with research stating that FWA positively affects work-life balance in the public sector [21]; [41]. However, this study contradicts research conducted by Hediningrum [33], [42], and [40].

The Effect of Work Overload on Work-Life Balance

The hypothesis test results show that work overload has a positive and significant effect on work-life balance among Civil Servants at the Regional Office of the Directorate General of Taxes in the Special Region of Yogyakarta. This finding indicates that increased perceived work overload is actually accompanied by an increase in work-life balance, which contradicts the initial hypothesis predicting a negative effect. Conceptually, work overload is generally understood as job demands exceeding an individual's capacity within a given period, whether in terms of workload, time pressure, task complexity, or multitasking [43]. In much literature, overload is potentially harmful to work-life balance as work consumes time, energy, and psychological space, disrupting family and social roles [44]. However, this study shows a different pattern, where increasing overload correlates with higher work-life balance.

This can be explained by the specific context of public sector organizations, especially Civil Servants at the Regional Office of the Directorate General of Taxes in the Special Region of Yogyakarta, which has formal work systems, strong standard procedures, and clear performance targets. In such an environment, high workload can stimulate employees to adjust their work behavior so that boundaries between work and personal life become more manageable. Literature shows that overload does not always harm work-life balance if employees have control over work arrangements, organizational support, and work systems that allow flexible work rhythm management [45]. In this study, the adequate FWA policy support (mean score 3.638) also strengthens employees' ability to balance roles despite high workload [46].

Descriptively, work overload among respondents is relatively high with a mean score of 3.690, especially on indicators of job complexity (WO.3.1 = 3.849) and simultaneous execution of several important tasks (WO.4.1 = 3.835). On the other hand, work-life balance is also in the fairly good category with a mean score of 3.276, with the highest value in the ability to divide time evenly (WLB.2.1 = 3.403). This pattern indicates that despite high job demands, employees are relatively capable of managing time and role division (Doerwald et al., 2021) [29]. This condition may occur because employees build adaptive strategies to maintain life balance such as more disciplined time management, work agenda arrangements, and use of digital work system support and team coordination [25].

Furthermore, respondent characteristics dominated by ages 31–50 and structural positions are relevant. Employees in this mid-career phase generally have the experience and competence to manage job and family demands, thus better able to cope and prioritize under overload conditions [31]. Under these circumstances, overload can encourage individuals to be more structured in managing work-life boundaries, ultimately enhancing work-life balance [13].

This finding aligns with studies finding that work overload can positively and significantly affect work-life balance under certain conditions, especially when individual control and organizational support are adequate [45]; [46]). However, this study rejects findings by Basyah et al. [47], Hediningrum [33], Ramadhan et al. [23], Putri & Primadineska [48], and Rambe & Pareke [49].

The Effect of Flexible Work Arrangement on Employee Performance Mediated by Work-Life Balance

The mediation test results show that flexible work arrangement (FWA) has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through work-life balance (WLB) among employees of the Regional Office of the Directorate General of Taxes, Special Region of Yogyakarta. This study confirms that flexible work policies not only have a direct impact on performance (H1), but also strengthen performance indirectly by improving employees' work-life balance. Improved implementation of FWA enhances employees' ability to manage the balance between work roles and personal life, which subsequently drives increased performance [39]. This pattern aligns with modern job design logic, where flexibility in time and location reduces role conflict, increases energy recovery, and maintains work focus, resulting in more effective work output and behaviors [38].

In the context of employees at the Regional Office of the Directorate General of Taxes, Special Region of Yogyakarta, this mediation pathway is consistent with the orientation of the policy in the Minister of State Apparatus Utilization and Bureaucratic Reform Regulation No. 4 of 2025, which positions FWA as a work pattern allowing adjustments in work time/location to achieve organizational targets, while also considering the balance between work life and social life of civil servants. Meaning, when FWA is implemented with clear systems and adequate support from the Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE), employees have a more realistic space to maintain role balance without losing productivity.

Descriptively, the FWA mean score of 3.638 indicates employees perceive flexible work implementation as good. The main strengths of FWA lie in support for work facilities (FWA.6.1 = 3.885) and continuity of work procedures (FWA.5.1 = 3.755). This is relevant because system and procedure support reduce “coordination costs” and administrative stress, enabling employees to better maintain WLB. On the other hand, WLB has a mean score of 3.276 (fairly good), especially on time management ability (WLB.2.1 = 3.403). This combination clarifies why mediation occurs: when flexibility is supported by clear facilities and work mechanisms, employees can manage time and energy more effectively, thus increasing balance and boosting performance [29]; [25].

Respondent characteristics further support the mediation explanation. Most respondents are aged 31–50 years and predominantly hold structural positions and mid-to-upper ranks. This group generally faces multi-role demands (work and family) and high work targets. In such conditions, FWA serves as an important instrument to reduce role pressure and maintain psychological stability, so employees can sustain performance without excessively sacrificing personal life [31].

These findings align with research showing that FWA indirectly improves performance by enhancing work-life balance [12]; [12]; [21]; [12]). This is because when employees have the freedom to regulate their work time, it increases balance both in work and personal environments, thereby improving performance [12]; [12].

The Effect of Work Overload on Employee Performance Mediated by Work-Life Balance

The indirect effect test results show that work overload (WO) positively and significantly affects employee performance (EP) through work-life balance (WLB). Thus, H7 is rejected because the direction of the effect is positive, while the research hypothesis (H7) explicitly predicted a negative effect. Therefore, even though the indirect effect is statistically significant, H7 is rejected due to inconsistency with the hypothesized effect direction.

Conceptually, H7 was based on the assumption that increased work overload would reduce work-life balance, which in turn would decrease employee performance [47]; [49]. However, this study shows a different pattern, where work overload is positively related to work-life balance, and work-life balance subsequently improves employee performance [50]. This can be explained by the specific organizational context and respondent characteristics. Civil servants at the Regional Office of the Directorate General of Taxes, Special Region of Yogyakarta, are dominated by middle to late career age groups and structural positions with mid-to-upper ranks. These employees generally have sufficient work experience, time management skills, and mature coping strategies to handle work pressure [13]. Under these conditions, a high workload does not automatically reduce work-life balance but encourages employees to adjust work rhythms, set priorities, and manage roles more disciplinarily [50].

Moreover, the presence of flexible work arrangement policies and electronic-based work systems in this office allows employees to manage workloads more flexibly. This condition potentially makes work overload not perceived as a pressure that damages life balance but as a manageable work demand. Consequently, work-life balance is maintained and even positively contributes to employee performance [44]. This study also rejects findings by Kelly & Moen [50], and Basyah et al. [47].

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study provides empirical evidence that flexible work arrangement (FWA) positively and significantly influences employee performance at the Regional Office of the Directorate General of Taxes in the Special Region of Yogyakarta. Additionally, work-life balance (WLB) also has a significant positive effect on employee performance, and it serves as an important mediating mechanism linking both flexible work arrangement and work overload to performance outcomes. Contrary to expectations, work overload does not have a direct significant negative effect on performance; instead, it relates positively to work-life balance and indirectly to performance, highlighting the complex nature of work demands and individual coping strategies within this public sector context. These findings emphasize the critical role of flexible work policies that enable employees to better manage the balance between work and personal life, thereby enhancing their overall performance. In particular, the presence of clear systems, adequate technological support, and structured procedures underpins successful implementation of flexible work arrangements. Moreover, employees with sufficient experience and maturity, often in structural roles, leverage these policies to adapt their work rhythms effectively, mitigating the potentially adverse effects of work overload.

From both practical and theoretical perspectives, these results suggest several important implications. Practically, the Regional Office should standardize FWA implementation across units to improve perceptions of schedule flexibility, establish clear boundary management to prevent work-life interference, and systematically manage work overload through workload redistribution. Additionally, programs supporting mental health and recovery should be enhanced to sustain employee well-being and productivity. Academically, future research should incorporate moderating variables such as perceived organizational support, self-efficacy, and coping strategies to better explain the positive relationship between work overload and work-life balance observed in this study. Furthermore, adopting multi-group analyses based on demographic and positional differences would provide deeper insights into how flexible work and overload affect diverse employee groups.

Limitations of this study include its cross-sectional design, focus on a single public institution limiting broader generalizability, and reliance on self-reported data, which may introduce biases. Future longitudinal and multi-institutional studies could address these gaps to enrich understanding of dynamic work-life interactions and performance in public organizations.

By integrating flexible work arrangements, effective work-life balance policies, and comprehensive workload management, public sector institutions—particularly in tax administration—can foster healthier, more productive work environments that sustain high employee performance and organizational effectiveness.

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